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**Study about musical structure parameters which have influence in a
tapping task**

Supervisor: Prof. Marta Olivetti Belardinelli

Assistent supervisor: Prof. Francesco Saverio Marucci

Graduating

Enrico Cupellini

Matr. n° 843829 (15177542)

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SUMMARY

This study deals with behavioral synchronization to a real musical fragment, whose structure might (or might not) be arranged according to western musical grammar. The literature has shown that rhythmical and metrical cues have the greatest importance in defining musical salience. On the other hand, only a few studies have paid attention to melody, timbre, intensity, and their mutual interactions during a synchronization performance.

In this work, I aimed at investigating the role of accents in timing judgments when a person is facing western or foreign meters. Furthermore, I was interested in investigating the synchronization biases related to music skills (western professional musicians vs. western naïve listeners). The literature shows that differences among these groups do exist, yet most of the studies typically use artificial cues (i.e., fragments without time expression), and in any case belonging to western music. According to the present study, musical expertise produces better performances only in presence of familiar meters. Indeed, when musicians face unfamiliar musical structures, they do not show significantly better performances as compared to naïve listeners. Experimental results show also that, given a tapping task on a meter structure, changes on melody, timbre and intensity cues do not cause different tapping performances, hence, they do not affect the decoding of timing.

CHAPTER 1

FUNDAMENTAL PSYCHOLOGICAL ELEMENTS IN MUSICAL TIME PERCEPTION

1.1 From physical percepts to perceptive objects

I was rather surprised the first time I saw a sound waveform, and even more when I looked at a sound's spectral representation. It is not obvious to realize that different sounds in an environment blend together into a unique pattern of oscillations before being captured by a receiver.

Psychology, along with other branches of knowledge, is involved in studying this phenomenon. Specifically, it tries to explain how sounds can be stored, processed and reproduced by human beings. Bregman (1990) studied how psychological events become perceptually salient, emerging from a raw acoustic stimulation. Our cognitive system is able to extract meaningful "figures" from a background, and Gestalt Psychology identified the so-called "laws of grouping".

For instance, according to the *Exclusive Allocation* law, a given sensory element cannot be used as part of two different figures at the same time when they are simultaneous (e.g., Rubin's illusion). Closer elements are likely to be joined together (Figure 1) as the *Proximity* principle predicts. In the auditory domain, two elements at a close pitch/time distance are judged to be part of the same auditory stream.

The *Similarity* principle links elements that share common features, as we recognize a melody when it is played by different instruments. The *Common Fate* principle claims that elements that move together are grouped together. The *Closure* principle allows us to manage fragmented percepts, for instance by filling gaps within the auditory streams, such as when a car hooter suddenly sounds on the background during a conversation. We group elements also according to their *spatial* arrangement.

When we identify patterns in our experiences, we can perform scheme-based recognitions. Bregman (1990, 1993) defines learning schemes as regular properties of the environment. Schemes create general expectancies (Dowling & Harwood, 1986), which might generate errors when the listener is located in an environment where such expectancies are misleading. Generally speaking, we can assume that the way we arrange bits of information will bias our future perception, comprehension and memory.

Figure 1. Dots represent a looping sequence of short pure tones with different pitches (Δf). The relationship between their frequency and temporal proximity will result into a trill or two parallel streams. An example of this phenomenon in a real musical context is when we listen to different melodies played together. They are better perceived when they are played in different registers. Conversely, when an instrument continues a melodic fragment started by another instrument (for instance in a baroque concert), we rather perceive a single continued melody that evolves.

1.2 Auditory streams in time

Some gestalt principles refer to local grouping (single notes or sounds), while other consider longer time spans. Some researches aimed at determining the shortest time to distinguish two different sounds (just noticeable difference), other aimed at establishing the laws of global integration of acoustic sequences (Warren & Ackroff, 1976; Warren, 1993).

Van Noorden (1975) claimed that within a sound sequence, rhythm and pitch interact together. He proved that the perception of rhythm can be influenced by pitch arrangement. Indeed, he showed that a change in the arrangement of auditory events affects grouping and rhythm perception. In one of his experiments, he created a sound sequence by alternating variable (V) and fixed (F) pitches. The resulting sequence looked like this:

....V F V -V F V....

The dashes here represent silent pauses (one every three sounds), each single event having the same duration (40 msec).

The variable pitch started from a very high frequency, gradually approached the fixed pitch, then gradually moved away (up to more than twelve semitones), then the cycle started again. When tones were close to each other, the listeners recognized a rhythmic trill (...V F V -V F V -V F V -...), when tones were far apart, the streams were perceived as separated, giving rise to a rhythm like the following:

....V -V -V -V -V -V -V -V -V....
 F —F —F —F —...

This result was consistent with the laws of grouping.

Van Noorden noticed that the interactions between durations and pitch separation led his subjects to perceive either a single auditory stream or two segregated streams. Figure 2 shows his results. The steeper blue line is called “temporal coherence boundary”; where short durations go along with higher pitch differences a voluntary perception of a single auditory stream is difficult. The flat blue line is called “fission boundary”, underneath which it is difficult to perceive two segregated streams. Between these two limits, both tasks can be achieved (ambiguous region).

Figure 2. Perception of a single stream cannot be achieved in presence of high pitch distances and short note durations (i.e., above the temporal coherence boundary). Conversely, two different streams cannot be perceived when pitch distance among notes is low and time is slow (i.e., below the fission boundary).

1.3 Phenomenal accents

According to a common view, time is considered as a linear flow. However, this is not the case of musical time, which is rather cyclical and allow us to experience different moments as repeated units of “present time” (Giannattasio, 1998). We perceive a musical excerpt as a whole event containing different sequences connected one another by so-called “structural invariants” (Dowling & Harwood, 1986), such as a specific key. Thanks to structural invariants, a schematic representation is possible. When structural invariants occur among different music pieces, we speak of a “style” (Narmour 1999).

Phenomenal accents are cues that bias the listener towards a given grouping segmentation (Jones, 1990a; Drake & Palmer, 1993), and once a segmentation occurs, such cues are used as reference points to process further groups.

Referring to both melodic and harmonic proprieties, Parncutt (1994) identifies four basic phenomenal accents (A_o): durational accents (A_d), dynamic accents (A_l), timbral accents (A_t), and pitch (or melodic) accents (A_p). Given a certain time (T) the following equation can be written:

$$A_o(T) = A_d(T) + A_l(T) + A_t(T) + A_p(T) + \text{interactions.}$$

Durational accents, also known as rhythmical accents (Jones, 1987; Drake & Palmer, 1993; Pfordresher, 2003), arise either from time changes between the onsets of two consecutive auditory events (inter-onset-interval, IOI), or from articulations such as *legato* / *staccato*, and are considered among the strongest phenomenal accents (Parncutt, 1994; Pfordresher, 2003). Amongst tones with the same pitch, amplitude and duration, Povel & Essens (1985) found that isolated tones (i.e., the second of a couple, or the first and last of a larger group) are perceived as accented events.

Dynamic accents arise from differences in tones amplitude. Parncutt (1994) claims that an increase of 2 dB for a tone in an isochronous sequence is enough to produce a dynamic accent, while an increase of 4 dB is needed to balance a competing durational accent.

Melodic accents come from leaps or changes in the melodic contour (Jones, 1990a; Drake & Palmer, 1993, Pfordresher, 2003).

Timbral accents are not precisely defined. Parncutt (1994) and Jones & Yee (1993) consider them as phenomenal accents, but they do not go into further details. Timbre is a multidimensional sound feature arising from the spectral content and its evolution over time, and independent from pitch content (Dowling & Harwood, 1986; Risset & Wessel, 1999).

In this text it has been proposed to define timbral accent as a modulation of spectral content over time among consecutive events due to the appearance of a new instrument, or to a difference in musical performance. For instance, vowels are recognized on the basis of the excitation of different formants in a frequency spectrum. Hence, we can create timbral accents by singing the same melody but using different vowels on the same note.

The perceived segmentation, the salience of certain events and the metrical pulsation are created by the recurrence of phenomenal accents (Parncutt, 1994; Drake & Palmer, 1993). On the other hand, perceptually relevant events tend to occur in stronger metrical positions (Povel & Essens, 1985; Parncutt, 1994), confirming the listener's expectancies and maintaining the coherence of the musical "message".

In the next paragraph it is introduced the “Dynamic Attending Theory” to describe the capability of attending to successive phenomenal accents in real situations. The basic idea behind this theory is that the listener creates expectancies related to precise future events on the basis of the regularities available in the auditory environment. This is possible thanks to the sensitivity of human attentional processes to environmental structures (Jones & Boltz, 1989; Large & Jones, 1999).

1.4 The Dynamic Attending Theory

1.4.1 Dynamic time structure

Mari Riess Jones was interested in studying the relationship between perceptive organization and time judgments. Unlike Van Noorden, she did not investigate gestalt principles, but rather learning schemes.

Time environmental structure is defined by the way in which auditory events are placed in time (Jones & Boltz, 1989). The environment is full of events whose structural coherence can be more or less low or high along a *continuum*.

Examples of highly structurally coherent events are language, body gestures and music, in which predictable temporal intervals allow the formation of expectations about the occurrence of subsequent events (Jones, 1990a). Expectations are abstractions that orient the listener’s attention in proximity of a subsequent event. When intervals are arranged by simple ratios (e.g., 2:1, 3:1) or by a sum of durations (e.g., 3+2), they are highly predictable.

Highly predictable structures are often hierarchical, implying that events are arranged at several levels. The main level in music is called “beat” or *tactus*, corresponding to the time period created by a listener that taps his/her foot in time with music (also called “reference period”).

Auditory structures might exhibit irregularities that struggle with the creation of expectancies, for instance, changes in speed or in events arrangement over time. Irregularities increase complexity and reduce structural coherency, so that it becomes less predictable. In such circumstances, the

listener reduces long-term expectations, and his/her attention will rather be engaged by short-term events.

Within naturalistic environments, both recurring and irregular events should be considered as meaningful. As Jones says: “characteristic motion patterns conveyed by body gestures supply critical information for observers who can recognize in these patterns a friend’s walk or a distinctive folk dance. Other gestures also transcribe characteristic velocity profiles (e.g., a speaker’s jaw motions or a tennis player’s swing). Many musical gestures, too, create velocity patterns because hands and fingers move over space, [...] a listener hears but does not necessarily view some musical performer, nevertheless information for something we can call an auditory motion is in the sound pattern” (pp. 209-210).

The rhythmic accents or tonal modulations in a given language do not have a firm hierarchical structure. However, it is likely that different articulatory speeds and intonations convey some information about a speaker’s intentions.

1.4.2 Synchronization to dynamic environmental structure

The process of attending to music can be modeled as an oscillatory activity emitted by biological (i.e., physical, not psychological) rhythms, where expectancies are created on the basis of periodicities within energy distribution (Jones & Boltz, 1989; Large & Jones, 1999; Drake, Jones & Baruch, 2000, Large & Palmer, 2002).

Inner rhythms might synchronize themselves with external recurrences. Initially, internal rhythms (i.e., the reference period) are independent from external rhythms. However, as time goes by the listener tunes onto recurrences similar to his/her inner rhythms (i.e., the reference level), which is called in many ways, such as beat, *tactus*, pulse or pace.

While the reference period is a subjective time, the reference level is an objective level of salience within a given hierarchical structure. By means of his/her tuning capabilities, the listener might

“share” (at least partially) the rhythmic pattern and the velocity patterns (or auditory motions) conveyed by music.

The reference period changes according to a subject’s age and expertise. Figure 3 shows changes of spontaneous tactus in subjects of different age and musical expertise cohorts (Drake, Jones e Baruch, 2000). Adults generally show a longer tactus (on average, around 600 msec) with respect to children, whereas standard deviations tend to increase with age and decrease with musical training.

Figure 3. Changes in spontaneous tactus with respect to age and musical expertise. Adults show longer spontaneous tactus with respect to children, and musicians show less fluctuations in a spontaneous tactus task with respect to non-musicians (Drake, Jones e Baruch, 2000).

Other works on spontaneous tapping in adults found an average tactus around 500-700 msec (Parncutt, 1994; Toiviainen & Snyder, 2003), and standard deviations around 420-1190 msec, corresponding to a range between 67 and 150 beats per minutes (BPM).

As we have seen, behavioral attunement is better with regular times. Jones et al. (2002) asked their subjects to compare the pitch of two tones separated by a distractor. Better performances occurred when distractors were evenly distributed between tones, so that the target tone was located where the listener expected it, i.e. around the attentional peak.

However, attentional rhythms might also adjust themselves to coherent phase or speed changes (Large & Jones, 1999), as well as to accidental or non-accidental temporary fluctuations. In fact, the attentional focus distributes over time according to a gaussian distribution rather than as an “all-or-

none” phenomenon, that is, a single attentional peak corresponds to an expectation spread over a temporal region with the highest probability in its middle point (Figure 4). The attentional focus increases as synchronization improves, and decreases as synchronization worsens. This implies that attentional focus is more affected by the violation of cultural expectancies, rather than by sequence variability per se”(Large & Jones, 1999).

Figure 4. Attentional energy in three different situations: $k=0$ no expectancy; $k=1$ slight increase in attentional focus; $k=4$ synchronization, attentional focus narrows around an area of high expectancy. (Large & Jones, 1999).

Furthermore, since attentional pulses can manage the fluctuations of a rhythm, and since several folk dances are made up by non-isochronous accents (London, 2004), we can argue that attentional mechanisms are triggered not only by steady beats. However, large deviations from expectancies generated without any coherence make structural complexity too high, and determine larger asynchronies when a subject is tuning to the rhythm (Jones & Boltz, 1989; Large & Palmer, 2002). The dynamic attending theory assumes that several inner rhythms (oscillators) are coupled with the reference level. Some of them (Parent) have a higher period, while some others (Child) have a shorter period with respect to the reference level (Figure 5). For complex rhythms, each of these inner rhythms might synchronize itself with a single periodicity of the outer rhythm. Inner oscillations are related to each other to create expectancy schemes, and practice might modify and refine such schemes.

Figure 5. Two correlated attentional pulses creating a metrical structure (Large & Palmer, 2002).

1.5 Expectancy schemes and metrical perception

Attentional expectations might arise according to durational cues (rhythmic accents), pitch changes (melodic accents), intensity changes (dynamic accents), timbre changes (timbral accents). This way, single tones, short melodies, or whole musical sequences can be part of a listener's expectations (Jones, 1990a).

Different types of accents can cooperate or can be antagonists. Normally, in music we find short-term recurrent patterns inside long-term patterns, giving rise to a hierarchy of expectations. For instance, let us consider a pattern of three notes inside a measure and repeated every two measures. Two different schemes of expectation are involved here, i.e. both shorter and longer periods.

Meter is the abstraction of hierarchical recurrences over time. It involves at least two levels of expectations, reference time level and the measure, namely a higher-order period based on a fixed number of beats. Meter has an integer number of pulses of reference level (tactus), and each of these pulses has a different degree of importance (Parncutt, 1994).

As we have seen, phenomenal accents underlie the perception of a reference pulse and a metrical structure (Drake & Palmer, 1993). We can describe the process as follows. Phenomenal accents break any coherence in the surrounding stimulation, and their perceptual organization brings to the formation of a "figure" against a background, catching a listener's attention. They define markers to tune onto (Jones, 1990a). They expand attention onto a larger time interval in which the listener can find recurrences according to his/her inner rhythms.

Time intervals defined by subsequent accents contribute to the perception of higher-level structures (Pfordresher, 2003). The metrical accent occurs where more cycles of recurrence overlap their regions of expectancy (Jones & Boltz, 1989).

Figure 6 shows a musical fragment of western music. Measures are separated by vertical lines, and each measure contains three pulses on the reference level (corresponding to eighth notes), one pulse on the higher level (dotted quarter notes, i.e. the measure), six pulses on the lower level (sixteenth notes).

Figure 6. Opening section from Two-Part Invention in D Minor, by J.S. Bach (Large & Palmer, 2002). Below the score, the schematic representation of three recurrence levels: measure (top), reference level (center), lower level (bottom).

Metrical accents are placed where more dots are vertically aligned (cf. lower part of Figure 6). The first position is a strong accent, the second and third-eighth notes are weaker accents, while the weakest notes are the sixteenth upbeats (Large & Palmer, 2002).

The stronger a metrical accent, the more likely it will be perceived as a downbeat position, i.e. the point where a listener probably taps his/her foot or finger (Parncutt, 1994). Expectations are not arranged in a rigid grid, rather, they can tune in to environmental changes (dynamic time structure). According to Giannattasio (1998), rhythm refers to a characteristic flow of events over time. Similarly, Large & Palmer (2002) describe rhythm as a temporal arrangement of event durations in an auditory sequence. Parncutt (1994) underlines the periodic perception behind the sense of rhythm.

We can consider rhythm as a specific organization of pitches, durations, dynamics and timbre, consistent with a tune's meter. Pauses as well are equally important structural elements for the creation of auditory events. Their occurrence upon the attentional peak prevent neither the formation of the reference pulse, nor rhythm perception¹ (Large & Palmer, 2002, cf. the last measure in Figure 6).

1.6 Time organization in not western cultures

While tactus might be found in nearly every musical culture (Cross, 2003), the organization of meter and rhythm is highly variable across different cultures.

As we have seen, meter is a hierarchical structure made up by combining reference levels of different lengths. Therefore, it involves at least two levels: the entire measure, as well as some isochronous or non-isochronous subcycles detected on the basis of metrical accents (London, 2004). European music culture developed symmetric and isochronous arrangements for metrical accents, often these arrangements are repetitions of binary or ternary groups inside a measure. Sachs (1979) claimed that in our culture the durational organization is based on (either real or just outlined) accents that create a series of regular paces, gathered in groups of two or more, where the first pace is always accented.

Other cultures (such as Balkan or north Indian) developed asymmetric accents organizations, for instance by grouping cells of different length together, often binary and ternary cells (London, 2004), but even more elements.

In the latter case, the tactus is non-isochronous (referring to Balkan music, Brailoiu 1973 speaks about "bi-chronous" meters). European listeners can perceive such pulse as unusual or ambiguous. Dowling & Harwood (1986) claim that most of aesthetic judgments made by musicians and naïve

¹ As for instance in reggae music, where the strong beat is played silently.

listeners relies on to what extent they are able to track the rhythmic accuracy of highly complex passages.

The psychological literature has just begun to investigate this problem. Some authors deny the existence of non-isochronous rhythms (see Moelants, 2003), considering them as mere expressive variations of isochronous rhythms. For instance, the wiener waltz would be a ternary isochronous rhythm in which the last quarter is delayed.

However, considering the differences between the structure and its expressive variations (Clarke, 1985), a western isochronous rhythm with expressive variations is still judged in a different way with respect to a non-isochronous system. In fact, asymmetric accents are perceived upbeat in an isochronous rhythm, but downbeat in a non-isochronous rhythm.

CHAPTER 2

EXPRESSIVE TIMING AND TIME COORDINATION

In this section, some experiments and theoretical approaches will be exposed to explain the production and re-production of musical time, then a methodology of research about behavioral synchronization will be presented.

2.1 Expressive musical performance

Musical execution (by naïves or expert musicians) is never strictly adherent to a score, because it is provided with expressivity. Expressive musical performance can involve many parameters like duration, inter onset intervals (called timing or *rubato*, Palmer 1989, Repp, 1997; Collier & Collier, 2002), intensity (Repp, 2000; Windsor & Clarke, 1997), pitch, articulation (like the *legato* and *staccato*, Drake & Palmer.1993), timbre (Palmer, 1996).

The deviations from a precise and regular execution are not generated by a background noise (randomness) rather they are useful informations for the listener (Large & Palmer, 2002). Most expressive variations are related to the musical structure (Palmer, 1989; Drake & Palmer, 1993; Penel & Drake, 1998), for instance we can mention the lengthening of notes durations on metrical accents, at the end of linked phrases, or in correspondence of cadence² movements. Other examples of expressive variations are the shorter durations on weak accents and the louder intensities on metrical and rhythmical accents. The last note in a rhythmic group is meanly played 10% longer and louder than the written value; notes on melodic accents are mainly played 3% longer than the written values.

² Karolyi (2000) defines cadence a well defined chord progression as I - IV - V - I, that has great importance in tonal grammar and often occurs at the end of a phrase. This particular is known as perfect cadence.

Another example of expressive execution related to musical structure is the lead voice anticipation, in other words the lead melody is likely to be played not only louder but earlier than other voices, during tonal melodies production (Palmer, 1996), this causes asynchronies into chords.

Palmer (1996) confirmed Todd's findings (1992) about timing execution for entire phrases in classical music, where notes with more intensity are played shorter of notes with less intensity. Moreover, Palmer found that within the phrases, notes on melodic accents are played louder.

2.1.1 Musical communication hypothesis

Some authors judged the systematic expressive variations as the performer's interpretation of the score, made by the musician to communicate some messages to the listener. Palmer (1989) for instance gave proof that musicians really do less timing expressions when they are asked to play mechanically; they would be aware of many variations and point out on a score.

The communication hypothesis claims that listeners understand better the musical structure thanks to these aids made by the performer who solves some possible uncertain passages, inside the score. On the other hand, the musician must own a deep knowledge of that music and must be well trained to technically control the musical instrument, further specific interpretations would affect the listener's representations.

Given that cultural influences and historical contexts are related to some kind of expressions, and that greater expertise provide better expressive freedom (Repp, 1997), the fame of some musician could be due to his personal music structures interpretations as well as to the technical ability. According to this thesis, Ashley (2002) investigated the art of jazz *rubato* measuring the expressive timing of some great soloists as Chet Baker, Art Farmer and Miles Davis on three different performances of the same ballad "My funny Valentine" and two performances of the song "Najma" made by John Coltrane.

In all these performances, the harmonic tones occurring downbeat (on strong metrical accents) were played shifted from the score position, more than non-harmonic notes. The author argued that musicians intentionally provided the dissonances with a different timing respect to the other tones. Anyway, as noticed by Kendall & Carterette (1990), the principal source of musical expression derives from implicit cognition, hardly explained by words. This implies that expression can be communicated (and taught) mainly by environmental interactions.

2.1.2 Perceptive hypothesis

Another perspective considers some variations as related to functional features of the auditory system (for instance some Inter Onset Intervals would be perceived shorter and than played longer as a perceptive compensation). The perceptive hypothesis (Penel & Drake, 1998) deals with low level processes of cognition (unlike the communication hypothesis) involved in local analyses of tones. This point of view looks at intrinsic and universal processes involved in auditory scene analysis.

The perceptive hypothesis becomes evident when musicians are asked to play expressively or mechanically. In these cases, many timing variations are nullified on the high level, but expressive timing variations related to local grouping remain. Therefore, Penel & Drake (1998) realized a model of music expression made by two levels:

- First level of time regularity extraction (reference level detection)
- Second level of grouping segmentation.

According to the theories proposed earlier (on first chapter) the listener synchronizes his own tactus upon regularity of phenomenal accents, moreover he divides the whole auditory stream into basic groups, according to the acoustical features of events. This way the listener arranges these groups in a hierarchical structure to process whole phrases and eventually the whole composition.

Time regularity extraction as the basic groups segmentation is due the low level processes (universal and ruled by gestalt principles). On the contrary, hierarchic segmentation comes from

higher-level processes (depending to culture and music training). Variations related to rhythmic groupings (made by durational accent organizations) would arise from low level processes, variations related to melodic groupings would be caused by mid-level processes, whereas variations related to hierarchic segmentation, group-final lengthening, cadence³ passages lengthening and the event's shortening on weak accents would arise from high level processes, based on expectations. The intensity variations (dynamic expression) would be under the voluntary control, indeed they tend to disappear when musicians play mechanically. Penel & Drake (*ibidem*) highlight how both the low and high level of processing work simultaneously in a performance.

2.2 Perception of timing expression

Perception of expressive variations may depend on music structure and on how the music is played, but at the end the music understanding process relies on a correct expression detection.

Clarke (1989) built some melodies with tones of equal duration. Some of these melodies were manipulated to provide them with a *rubato* timing, while other were provided with metronomic timing; some of them were tonal, other were atonal melodies. One note inside these melodies could be lengthened of 10, 20, 30, 40 or 50 msec respect to the others. He asked the subjects to recognize the shifted tone in time. Subjects were able to recognize the time changes over 20 msec. Tonal and atonal melodies received the same results, while for *rubato* melodies the time changes were more difficult to catch.

Repp (1998, 1999) found that listener's skill to detect deviations from a metronomic time depends to the listener's expectancies to find expressive variations. For instance, if we expect a slowdown, we worse detect a tone extension, on the contrary we better detect a tone reduction (and vice versa if we expect a speed up). Besides, Repp found that the perception of time variations is not related to

³ See Agamennone et al. (1991) for further readings on cadence in Ethnomusicology. See Larson (2002) For a review of researches in Psychology.

the level of music training, indeed only completely untrained participants showed a lower skill for timing detection.

Even Kendall & Carterette (1990) found that trained and untrained listeners can discern different expressive intensions played by violin, trumpet, clarinet, oboe and piano.

Anyway a regular accent structure, that leads the listener to a meter construction, increases the likelihood of correct perceptions and reproduction of time patterns (Drake & Palmer, 1993), instead, an extreme complex accent structure causes the lower prediction of future events and causes an attentional restriction to neighbor tones (Jones, 1990a; Jones e al., 2002).

Two theoretic approach exist: the first says that different accent structures can be independently perceived (Monahan & Carterette, 1985; Palmer & Krumhansl, 1987) (for instance temporal and pitch structures), the second approach supports phenomenal integration. According to the last position, the perception of one structure affects others, so that their conflict will compromise the pattern perception/reproduction (Jones, Boltz & Kidd, 1982; Clarke, 1985).

2.2.1 Cognitive representation and reproduction of musical structure

Drake & Palmer (1993) surveyed how pianists emphasize music accents when they reproduce sequences with different complexity, having isolated or combined accent structures, in agreement or conflicting each other. The authors created two experimental groups: pianists among the first group played only single accent structures, pianist among the second group played combined accents structures, either with coinciding or conflicting accent structures. The music sequences could be made of different levels of complexity.

In all musical contexts, similar systematic variations were observed: the pianists played the same variations when the music sequences to play had single accent structure or different kind of accents combined together. The rhythmic and metric accents caused stronger timing variations respect to melodic accent structures.

The variations played on the rhythmic and metric accents were more frequently found respect to the variations played on the melodic accent structure, when these two occurred in conflict each other. Musicians performed longer tones (longer Inter Onset Interval), louder and more *legato* tones as these tones occurred on rhythmic and metric accents; they performed lower variations on melodic accents. Therefore the authors assessed the rhythmic and metric structures as dominant on others.

According to Meyer & Palmer (2003), the representation of temporal structures like rhythm and meter, is abstract (high level of processing), independent from the actual gesture and from the motor program involved in that rhythmic pattern.

In Meyer & Palmer's experiments, some skilled adult pianists were trained to play a melody, then during successive tasks, they were asked to play the same melody changing the hand and fingering, the rhythm structure, or the meter organization (4/4 versus 3/4).

Once participants learned the melody, they performed the modified task while the authors measured the errors made and the speed of reproduction, considered as indexes of scheme transfer between known and novel learning (Palmer & Meyer, 2000). The findings showed that motor features played a smaller role in transfer of knowledge respect to rhythmical and metrical cues, at least for expert musicians. This means that musicians represent the melody at abstract level, independently from the particular effector involved; less skilled musicians instead represent melodies either at motor and at abstract level.

The authors noticed no significant expressive changes in 4/4 and 3/4 meter, but it could be argued that both the meters were familiar to the subjects.

All these studies highlight the importance of perceptive organization in producing expressive timing variations. Therefore, we can consider that different accent structures can lead to different variations, related to the tune we are listening. We can argue the supremacy of rhythmical and metrical structures over melodic structures in causing variations, but we do not know exactly the supremacy over dynamic and timbre accent structures, as well as the possible interaction between them.

2.3 Entrainment to an external rhythm

According to Andolfi (2000), the creation of a shared time frame is critically important for communicative and learning purposes. Indeed, as he states: “the attempt to synchronize the movements can be considered one of the main processes that aim to create a common communication module”, “the rhythms of movements become a supplemental information [to the words, *Ed.*] for the observer and for the actors inside an interaction. They reveal the emotional level of acceptance/rejection, distance/proximity among people”. (Andolfi, 2000, pag 141-142)

Several researches focused on synchronization, imitation of expressions, gestures, and postures among people involved within an interaction. Rizzolatti et al. (1999) discovered the Mirror Neurons, a neuronal system devoted to match the observation and execution of oriented actions; this system could be used in resonance behaviors, social understanding and empathy.

The infant-research highlights the relationship between the infant and his caregiver, starting from the first day of birth, as a unit of mutual stimulation and behavioral regulation (Lichtenberg, 1995). Trehub (2003) and Cross (2003) speak of a natural musicality for the human behavior, for instance the lallation is a musical language made by caregivers of every culture⁴.

In clinical experience we can mention the resonance among the members of a group, the concept of “syncretic sociality” (Neri, 1998), that is a deep and not verbal linkage among people.

Dynamic attending theory describes the synchronization to an external rhythm. In a real musical context all the participants coordinate their inner rhythms to get a common expressive pulsation, defined as *groove* by Iyer (2002).

Schogler (1999) studied the coordination during improvisation of jazz duets, he showed how musicians adjust their own rhythms and gesture each other to reach a unique music narration.

⁴ Cross (2003) speaks about the rhythmicity of caregiver- interaction: the baby can follow and respond in kind to temporal regularities, in vocalisations and movements and in time to initiate temporally regular sets of vocalizations and movements, and this is crucial to develop significative and communicative capacities. Time sharing behaviors are natural and embodied skills that allows the right interaction of affect states.

2.3.1 Tapping task: an experimental method to investigate the time entrainment.

Drake and Bertrand (2003) consider the tapping task an easy way to study the synchronization process. It is usually made up of a task where the subject is asked to listen to the music and tap freely and rhythmically on a computer keyboard.

From mid 50' on, tapping task was used to study both the spontaneous tactus without an external stimulus, both the synchronization process to an outer rhythm (Dowling & Harwood 1986, for a review of the researches). Often, sequences of synthetic sounds without expressiveness were used as stimuli.

Recently Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000) asked to musicians and naïve subjects to perform a tapping task to synchronize on music sequences with or without expressive timing and with or without intensity accents. They found that synchronization in general was better for mechanical timed music and best for accented versions.

The tapping task on expressive music was performed on more reference levels respect that executed on mechanical versions. Musicians achieve a better synchronization, carried on higher reference level regard to naïves, in other words their tapping task had longer periods and was more precise respect to that performed by not musicians.

Musicians respect to not musicians, showed more extended representations about music hierarchic levels, in fact they could synchronize themselves on more reference levels respect to naïves if they were asked to do that. They could focus their attention, and therefore synchronise on more recurrent levels respect to naïves.

CHAPTER 3

THE EXPERIMENT

3.1 Introduction

In first and second chapter have been discussed the importance of accent structures in music experience: the accents arise from physical changes occurring in auditory streams (Drake & Palmer, 1993); accents are some meaningful points for cognition (Cooper & Meyer, 1960) in fact they affect segmentation of auditory stream into groups (Bregman, 1990).

Grouping mechanisms work at different levels, there are local groups and hierarchic segmentation groups (Penel & Drake, 1998). Rhythmic and metric accents are in certain way dominant over other accents (Meyer & Palmer, 2003), but at present days it is not clear the influence of dynamic and timbre accents for musical time codification. Moreover, it is not well defined the reciprocal influence that different accent structures have, where one kind of accent is simultaneous or conflicting with other structures.

Jones (1990b) claims that temporal complexity is inversely proportional to long time expectations about future events.

Literature often considered structural complexity as related to the number of not coincidental accents occurring together (Drake & Palmer, 1993; Drake, Penel & Bigand, 2000; Pfordresher, 2003; Meyer & Palmer, 2003). Few researches focused on studying the time codification of accent structures, in not western music.

We found that literature is extensively involved on researches with western music structures (4/4 or 3/4 meters), therefore we can argue that studies like Meyer & Palmer (2003) give proof of the dominance of rhythmic organization over metric organization since their meters are both familiar. For these reason I was aimed at researching the influences of culturally defined time structures, in order to detect some possible discrepancy.

During the previous chapter I described the tapping task as a method to study the referent period (tactus), spontaneously produced with or without the synchronization to an external rhythm.

Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000) studied the tapping performance over real music (with expressive timing). Their results showed that musicians achieve a better and faster synchronization respect to naïve subjects and that synchronization is better for metronomic excerpts (with no expressive timing) respect to expressive stimuli.

Literature shows that inter tapping intervals (ITI) has more variability (less precise) on expressive fragments than on mechanical excerpts, further the tapping frequencies delivered by musicians were lower (longer tapping periods) than those by naïve subjects.

Drake, Jones e Baruch (2000) proved that musicians perform more precise ITI (with less standard deviation) respect to naïves; on the other hand, musicians can synchronize themselves on different reference levels respect to naïves (Drake, Penel & Bigand, 2000).

3.2 Experimental hypotheses

I chose a free tapping task to investigate the synchronization to a real music excerpt. The index of good synchronization (dependent variable) was the distance between music accents and tapping times, so the closer tapping marks respect to the accent in time, the more precise the behavioral synchronization was judged. I designed the experiment on two experimental groups: naïves and well trained musicians.

Each group was studied on eleven different conditions as explained below, according to the accent structure, because I was aimed at studying the role of each accent structure in a synchronization task.

Melodic, dynamic and timbral accent structures could be presented in one of the following levels of complexity: 1) original accent structure, 2) structure without accents, 3) structure containing complex and incoherent accent organization. The time structure could be presented as original (with a natural timing expression) or without timing expression.

Assuming that timing perception is made possible by physical and cultural constraints, I chose two musical excerpts: one with a western meter, the other with a foreign meter; the same manipulations were reproduced on the familiar and unfamiliar fragment of music. I used digital signal processing to alter the accent structure on the musical excerpts as explained below.

The dependent variable (time distances between accent and tapping marks) has some components, which can be observed:

- The beginning of tapping: which is the time before the subject starts to tap, at the beginning of the experimental task, while he is listening to the stimulus.
- The speed of synchronization: which is the time elapsed from the beginning of tapping before the entrainment to the rhythms.
- The number of modal distributions of tapping periods (ITI).
- The number of rhythmical patterns the subjects express during the experimental task.
- The accuracy of tapping respect to the musical excerpt.

The experimental hypotheses claimed that modifications of an accent structure can bias the expectancies of recurring events. Modifications of accent structures should change also the expectations of expressive timing. As a consequence, the most involved accent structures in timing expression should bias the synchronization task, when they are modified.

Finally, it was assumed that well trained musicians would perform a better task respect to not musicians.

3.3 Experimental Conditions

Two real musical excerpts were chosen and processed, so that each accent structure could change independently from other accents.

From each excerpt I made eleven versions:

- 1) Original (OR)
- 2) Without expressive timing (NE)
- 3) Without dynamic accent structure (ND)
- 4) Without pitch accent structure (NM)
- 5) Without timbre accent structure (NT)
- 6) Containing a not coherent dynamic structure (D)
- 7) Containing a not coherent melodic structure (M)
- 8) Containing a not coherent timbre structure (T)
- 9) Without both melodic and timbre structure (NTM)
- 10) Without both melodic and dynamic structure (NDM)
- 11) Without both dynamic and timbre structure (NTD)

I used digital signal processing to create versions that invalidate the listener's expectancies, for example the occurrence of louder tones on metrical accents.

Modifications erased the physical differences of accent structures, or they created sequences of accents with no predictable recurrence.

I supposed that versions with lacks of one accent structure, have less complexity respect to versions with incoherent accent structures, at the same time versions with the lack of two accent structures have less complexity respect to versions with the lack of one accent structure (figure 7).

Figure 7. The different versions of one stimulus, according to the degree of structural complexity.

By giving these conditions, two kinds of results could be imagined about the performances: according to Drake & Palmer (1993) (§2.2), different accent structures are perceived independently each other (independence of perception). Therefore, the modification of one structure will not influence the perception of other structures. This assumption implies that subjects will rely on other coherent structures to accomplish the synchronization task.

The second alternative was a phenomenal integration between accents; therefore, structure modification would affect the perception of other accent structures. Thus the tapping performances would be affected according to the structure importance. Figure 8 shows the alternative ways of perception.

Figure 8. Elements that could be modified in experimental musical excerpts: dynamic accent structure, pitch accent structure, timbre accent structure. When one structure is modified, the same performance can occur if a perceptive independence exists; on the contrary, a different performance can occur if a phenomenal integration exists.

To have a complete range of experimental conditions, I made also a version without timing variability: following Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000) I supposed that this version would provide a better synchronization.

3.4 Materials

The experimental stimuli were two real musical fragments where a Jews harp plays (figure 9). Both the stimuli have been recorded in India (Rajasthan). The first (track A) has been picked from the

CD “*Instruments de Musique du Monde*”, made by “*Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique et du Musée de L’Homme*” in 1990. The second excerpt (track B) belonged to the CD “*The Big Bang - in the beginning was the drum*”, volume 2, made by “*Ellipsis Arts*” in 1994. These two tracks had the same duration (nearly a minute), the same loudness, both the instruments played on the same tonal register.

Figure 9. Jews harp

Track A was structured on an isochronous meter: 4/4, while the track B had a not isochronous meter, organized by a ternary cell, followed by two binary cells (3+2 meter).

This resembled an Aksak rhythm (Brailoiu 1973) even if this music came from a different geographical region. Giving their structure the track A was the familiar item (according to the European music culture), the track B was instead the unfamiliar item (belonging to a foreign music culture).

3.4.1 Items selection

In order to study the behavioral synchronization, I looked for a real music fragment (the recording of a human performance with a natural expressive timing), played with a solo instrument owning percussive character but with pitch and timbre richness. Instruments like drums would have been excellent for percussive features but poor in pitch variations, on the other hand the sound of the voice, which has rich timbre and pitch expression, shows on the other hand a slow attack, therefore it would have been a bad stimulus to measure the level of synchronization on.

The sound of Jews harp instead has a sharp attack, a timbre richness that can be modulated according to the player skills. The sound produced has a fundamental harmonic and a number of

overtones, which can be excited moving the tongue to produce a number of pitches correlated to the fundamental sound. The timbre can change and become bright or dark, resembling a wah-wah effect.

Instrument's loudness, timbre and register are correlated to the material it is built with, as well as to the performer skills. However, two kinds of registers can be recognized: low and high register, one octave apart ⁵.

Figure 10 shows three distributions of frequencies referring to track A: on the left side the spectral content of the entire track is shown, while the middle and the right side spectral content shows two consecutive tones played.

Figure 10. Spectral content of the entire track A on the left. Two consecutive single tones on the middle and on the right. It can be noticed that all the sounds arise from different excitations of identical overtones. (FFT with a resolution of 5,38 Hz).

It can be noticed how different tones can be produced by the overtones excitation on a fixed series of harmonics. The musician can obtain this effect by modifying the mouth opening.

3.4.2 Items analysis

Tracks A and B were similar and comparable, both in the original version and in the modified versions: the same instrument played with the same timbre and the same technique of execution.

The speed of execution was similar between tracks. The first track contained 26 measures (of four quarter each). The quarter note was meanly 520 msec, the half measure was meanly 1040 msec. The

⁵ References about Jews harp are listed at the end of the book.

second track was made up of 46 measures (of 3+2+2 octaves). The measure lasted meanly 1190 msec. The figure 11 shows the metrical structure of track A and B.

Figure 11. Metrical structure of track A (one measure on the left) and track B (two measures on the right).

The meter is subdivided in four different recurrence levels, from the events level to the measure.

The tracks had not durational accents, in other words all events were equally spaced into the time grid and no pause occurred. The meter was structured by dynamic, pitch and timbre accents. A single event measured meanly 130 msec for track A and meanly 170 msec for track B.

The timing of track A was little more variable than track B, but track A had an isochronous meter (familiar).

The tonal registers were quite the same: track A had the fundamental pitch around 123 Hz (near to B2 musical tone), track B had the fundamental pitch around 150 Hz (near to D3 musical tone). This means that frequency excitations and melodic contours were similar for both the tracks.

3.4.3 Manipulations ⁶

The manipulations were made by digital signal processing, using two softwares: Cubase SX 1.06 and Melodyne 1.1.

The following images show some spectrographs resulting from track B. The X axis represents the time flow (from left to right), the Y axis represents the frequency (linear scale from 0 to 22000 Hz). The colors map the spectral energy (frequency amplitude) from blue (low energy) to yellow/red (high energy).

Original versions:

Figure 12. Original version spectrogram

the original files were converted from 16 to 24 bit for higher accuracy of processing (maintaining the sample rate to 44.1 kHz). Some important features were matched between track A and B: the spectral significant range was matched, the frequencies under 60 Hz were eliminated because contained only noise (according to Rasch & Plomp 1999).

The spatialization was matched between the track A and B using the plug-in “Ozone Izotope 2”.

The Overall amplitude and the loudness were matched between the tracks as well.

These operations were conducted according to Vastfjall, Larsson and Kleiner (2002) to reduce listener’s reactions to these unwanted variables.

Figure 13. Spectrogram without pitch accent structure.

The resulting files were used as a model for further operations.

Removal of pitch structure:

According to acoustical laws earlier explained, the tonal changes relies in Jews harps upon harmonics modulations, over a fixed fundamental frequency. Thanks to the references

⁶ See appendix A for a comprehensive explanation of the digital signal processing used in content manipulations.

found on the web (see References section at the end of the book), I found that harmonics involved in pitch modulation are those from the fourth to the eighth one for low register and from the eighth to the sixteenth one for the high register.

Therefore, the pitch accents were removed by deleting the frequencies between the fifth and sixteenth harmonics with a graphic equalizer, as the Figure 13 shows the result.

This way the two excerpts played on a fixed pitch throughout the entire track, maintaining the original dynamic, timbre, rhythm and meter structure.

Not coherent pitch structure:

The software Melodine was used to change the pitch structure (see Appendix A for detailed informations). I chose only pitches that Jews harp can produce, recreating a musical scale on the same basis exposed earlier (§ 3.4.1), it was a scale built from the eighth to the sixteenth harmonic. Manipulations were made to nullify the expectations of western melodies (Agamennone et al. 1991, Dowling & Harwood 1986), for instance the relevant pitches in the scale not occurred on metrical accents. Manipulations were made to remove any recurrence among tones. The same melodic contour was given to both the excerpts.

To avoid the phenomenon of stream segregation (Bregman 1990) that leads to changes of rhythm perception (Van Noorden, 1975 as described in first chapter), the manipulations didn't involve successive tones far more than 560 cents each other, that means leaps were no greater than five semitones and a half.

This value is under the limit of temporal coherency (§1.2) in fact the shortest event for track A lasts 130 msec and the shortest event for track B lasts 170 msec.

Avoidance of dynamics structure:

Figure 14. Spectrogram without dynamic accent structure.

Using Cubase SX software, each event was separated from others and normalized to 0 dB. Then a compressor whose threshold set to -15 dB and ratio set 8:1 processed the whole track. This way all tones had the same intensity maintaining the other parameters unchanged.

Figure 15. Spectrogram with not coherent dynamic structure.

Not coherent dynamic structure:

All events were separated, then each event was assigned to a random change in amplitude (a different dynamic value occurred for each event).

This process aimed at nullifying the western expectations that claim the first tone in a measure to be louder than other tones.

Intensity changes were made between 0 and -11dB. The same dynamic range was present into the original tracks.

Avoidance of timbre structure:

Figure 16. Spectrogram without timbre accent structure.

According to chapter §1.3, I considered the timbre accent as the change in the spectral content over consecutive events, independently from pitch.

The spectral content was matched with an envelope follower filter. By consequence, every event onset had the same spectral excursion. Further the spectral content under the eighth and

above the sixteenth harmonic was erased because they don't affect the melody structure, only the timbre.

Not coherent timbre structure:

Timbre modulations, without any recurrence were created using an automated parametric equalizer. The timbre excursion was set between 150 and 4000 Hz.

Avoidance of timing variations:

Using Melodyne software, each event was sampled and it was stretched to a fixed duration (the mean value of that track).

In any case the signal processing was performed to nullify expectations of hierarchic organization (Jones & Boltz 1989; Parncutt, 1994), not to create conflicts to the gestalt principles, as for instance the stream segregation (Van Noorden 1975). I tried to respect the range of natural instrument capability.

3.5 Subjects

I was aimed in studying the rhythm entrainment performed by subjects with different levels of music expertise.

Given that different music expertise lead to different kinds of behavioral synchronization (Drake, Penel & Bigand, 2000), I gathered two experimental groups: naïves, comprising people without any deep music scholarship who never played an instrument, and experts, comprising people who have played an instrument for more than five years, practicing at least 10 hours per week.

Naïves were 66 people, 22 male and 44 female, from 19 to 59 years old, 27 years old on average. They all had a western music culture, some of them were university students.

Experts were 22 people, 16 male and 6 female, from 18 to 59 years old, 28 years old on average and they meanly have studied music for 12,5 years. They all had a western music culture, some of them were students at the Conservatory and others were music teachers or professional musicians.

3.6 Procedure

At the beginning of the experiment, a written document was given to the subjects, with the following presentation:

“Thanks for participating to this experiment, this is a study on music rhythm. I will propose you two excerpts: while listening to the music, you must push on the computer’s button, in rhythm with music, precise as much as you can, using only one finger of one hand.

- 1) I advice to push the button with a rate that well suits your subjective rhythm.
- 2) I simply ask to keep the time, not to improvise over the music.
- 3) When you will listen the music, start to perform the task, as soon as you can, aware to follow the timing expression until the end of the music. During the task it will not occur any trick or other unattended event.

If something is unclear about your task, please ask to the operator. Now you can practice on a trial excerpt before performing the experimental task”.

The subjects held on a professional pair of headphones to listen the music during the tasks. They could adjust the volume as they wished during the trial task. Trial and experimental tasks were normalized at the same volumes.

The experimental instructions to the subjects were extracted from Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000), I changed only the expression “tap regularly and in synchrony with the music” with “symply keep the time, not improvise” because the track B had a not-isochronous rhythm.

The trial excerpt was a recording personally made of the Senegalese percussionist Sena M’Baye playing his djembè. This excerpt had the same duration respect to the experimental tracks, it was chosen because it owns a rhythm far from the western culture.

The order of presentation about the experimental tracks was random. Subjects heard only one version of track A and one version of track B chosen randomly. Between the tracks the subjects had a little rest.

At the end of the tasks a semi-structured interview was conducted, I asked the following questions to the participants:

- How did you feel in keeping the time with the experimental tracks?
- Could you maintain the rhythm with the first and the second experimental track? What is your opinion about the accuracy of your performance?
- Do you want express your opinion or any comment regarding the trial or the experimental tracks?
- What kind of feelings the experimental tracks did suggest to you?
- It was easy keep the time by using a button of the computer keyboard?

3.7 Experimental apparatus

I used a Comex Pentium 4 laptop to carry on the experiment, with Windows XP *Home Edition* as operational system. Participants held a pair of AKG K141 headphones.

The laptop caused low level of noises respect to a desktop computer, reducing unwanted noises (Vastfjall e al., 2002).

I created an experimental software using Max/MSP programming environment. By the software the tracks were reproduced and the tapping times recorded; the software architecture is explained in Appendix B at the end of the book.

The tapping times were recorded on a text file, and then they were analyzed.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS, DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION

4.1 Methods of analysis

I chose to assess the beginning of a tapping performance separated from the first emergence of a pattern; the delay time between these two events was considered as an index of speed of synchronization.

According to the experimental design, the emergence of a tapping pattern was considered the first of three or more recurrent cycles. For isochronous tapping it was enough to find three successive equal Inter Tapping Intervals (ITI); for not-isochronous tapping it was required to find three repetitions of the same tapping structure.

The number of patterns produced by a subject during the tapping task was another variable examined. According to the experimental design, this variable was considered as correlated to the cognitive schemes variability during the synchronization task.

Further, I measured the number of ITI modes on a distribution of frequencies. All the ITI records were grouped into classes of 20 msec each. Two resulting histograms are showed in figure 17, where the X axis represents the time classes, the Y axis represents the number of inter tapping intervals, collected during the performance for each class. The number of modes informs about the used tapping pattern: a single mode means that the subject executed an isochronous pattern, two modes means that the subject performed a pattern of short and long ITI, and so on.

Figure 17. The ITI distribution of frequencies for an isochronous tapping performance on the left and not-isochronous tapping performance on the right.

The detailed criterion to measure the tapping accuracy versus the music events is exposed below. Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000); Drake, Jones & Baruch (2001) judged as successful the tapping laying upon the accents reference levels, with a tolerance of $\pm 10\%$ respect to the interval duration. This way they obtained a percentage of successful synchronization to a given reference level. This criterion didn't suit well the goals of the present research: first because the authors asked to perform a regular and isochronous tapping instead I did not ask the same, given that the track B had a not-isochronous meter and such a request would have biased the performances. Furthermore, the cited criterion did not describe the subjective style in keeping time but only it provided an index of percentage of fitting into a given reference level, so it is a raw measure to judge the influence of a certain accent structure on the timing perception. Therefore, I chose the following criterion to judge the tapping accuracy:

As Rosenthal (1992) claimed, in a piece of music we can find at least three levels: the Tactus, the Child and the Parent. In a symmetric meter, the Inter Onset Intervals (IOIs) referring to the Child level has half the duration of Tactus level IOIs, and the latters have half the duration respect to the Parent level IOIs. In an asymmetric meter, inter onset intervals ratios among levels depend upon the accent subdivisions.

On the other hand, if a subject performs an isochronous pattern, the produced ITIs belong to a reference level; if the subject performs a not-isochronous pattern, the tapping marks belong to more than one reference level, but we can detect those levels from the ITI duration.

Given that a tapping pattern is always related to one or more reference levels, I considered a number of classes for Track A and B as it is described in table 1.

Once grouped each ITI record in classes, I measured the following indexes:

- Tapping anticipation or delay respect to the corresponding event position.
- Tapping standard deviation respect to the events positions. This is correlated to the tapping precision.
- The main time distance from music events and tapping times. This is related to the tapping accuracy.
- The ITI times membership in one or more meter's reference levels.

TRACK A (OR) levels	TRACK A (NE) levels	TRACK B (OR) levels	TRACK B (NE) levels
Measure: $ITI \geq 787$ ms	Measure: $ITI \geq 788$ ms	Measure: $ITI \geq 915$ ms	Measure: $ITI \geq 938$ ms
2nd higher level: $405 \text{ ms} \leq ITI < 787 \text{ ms}$	2nd higher level: $410 \text{ ms} \leq ITI < 788 \text{ ms}$	1st and 2nd higher level: $254 \text{ ms} \leq ITI < 915 \text{ ms}$	1st and 2nd higher level: $261 \text{ ms} \leq ITI < 938 \text{ ms}$
1st higher level: $202 \text{ ms} \leq ITI < 405 \text{ ms}$	1st higher level: $201 \text{ ms} \leq ITI < 410 \text{ ms}$		
Events level: $ITI < 202$ ms	Events level: $ITI < 201$ ms	Events level: $ITI < 254$ ms	Events level: $ITI < 261$ ms

Table 1: Time classes to group the Inter Tapping Intervals (ITI) produced by subjects. Two reference levels of track B were merged together because the meter of this track contained ternary and binary units (i.e., 3+2+2). Time classes are slightly different between expressive excerpt and those without time expression (NE items, see chapter 3).

Even other studies (for instance Repp, 1999) used the tapping anticipation/delay to measure the degree of precision. Usually it is noticed an anticipation effect during the experimental tapping performances (Ascherleben & Prinz, 1995).

Ashley (2002) e Schogler (1999) judged the tapping standard deviation as inversely related to the level of rhythm control.

4.2 Results

Four participants were kept out from data analysis: a woman with partial loss of hearing, a man who performed the tapping task using two fingers and two participants who stop and restart the task during the experiment.

4.2.1 Role of musical training

The experimental data analysis revealed as a first significant result that naïve subjects began the tapping task earlier than expert subjects ($F(1, 132)=8,9520, p<0,01$).

The mean time of the first tap (the first time the keyboard's button was clicked during the experimental task) was 1,86 seconds after the beginning of music for naïve group and 2,95 seconds for the experts. There are no significant differences respect to the track.

There are no significant differences between groups respect to the speed of synchronization, once the first tap was made, the naïves took 2,45 seconds to perform the same pattern for three consecutive times, while the experts took 3,04 seconds meanly.

Apart the initial behavior, during the entire performance the experts had less tapping pattern variability than naïve subjects, in fact they used less tapping patterns ($F(1, 132)=12,232, p<0,01$).

The criterion to assess a pattern change, as for the first pattern emergence, was the evidence of three recurrent cycles of the same kind of ITIs. Experts made meanly 1,68 patterns, naïves 3,3 patterns.

The figure 18 shows this result.

Figure 18. Relation between expertise (0=naïve, 1=experts) and number of produced patterns during the experimental task.

The tapping times made by experts are closer to the music accents ($F(1, 132)=6,0338, p<0,05$), thus they achieved a better tapping accuracy respect to the naïves.

During a single performance, the sum of time differences between tapping times and a music event's onsets was mainly 7069 milliseconds for experts and 8377 milliseconds for naïves. Figure 19 shows this relation.

Figure 19. Accumulated time differences (milliseconds) between groups (inverse index of tapping accuracy) (0=naïve, 1=expert)

Another significant difference between groups was the anticipation/delays ratio versus the event onsets: experts constantly tapped their finger before the music event, in contrast to naïve subjects ($F(1, 132)=37,922, p<0,01$). The 68% of tapping records made by experts was in advance respect to the 53% of tapping records made by naïves. Figure 20 shows this result.

As a consequence, the tapping performance made by experts had less standard deviation respect to naïve's performance ($F(1, 132)=5,9014, p<0,05$). As mentioned earlier, the standard deviation index is related to tapping precision.

Figure 20. Relation between tapping anticipation and expertise (0=naïve, 1=expert)

During the performance on both the experimental tracks, experts produced longer periods of tapping respect to naïves, figures 21a and 21b show the results divided for each recurrence level.

In both the tracks, naïves tapped on the shortest level (events level) more than experts ($F(1, 132)=10,141, p<0,01$).

On track A the first higher level is played more by naïves than by experts ($F(1, 86)=4,0087, p<0,05$), on the contrary the second higher level is played more by experts ($F(1, 86)=5,3340, p<0,05$).

Figure 21a., Distribution of ITI frequencies on each reference level of track A. Experts tapped more on second higher level. On the contrary naïves tapped more on shortest level (“events”) and on first higher level.

Figure 21b. Distribution of ITI frequencies on each reference level of track B. Naïves tapped more on shortest level (“events”). Experts had the tendency to play more on the higher levels respect to naïves but the differences are not significant ($F(1, 86)=3,8745, p=0,052$).

4.2.2 Cultural influences

The ITI distributions of frequencies on track A had less modes respect to track B ($F(1, 132)=6,0468, p<0,05$). The average of modes was 1,4 for track A and 1,7 for track B. This means that on track B the subjects likely performed a not isochronous tapping behavior.

Moreover the tapping times on track A were closer to the music accents respect to the tapping on track B ($F(1, 132)=57,609, p<0,01$). The accumulated distances on track A were meanly 5960 milliseconds, while the distances on track B were meanly 10140, as figure 22 shows.

Figure 22.
Accumulated distances of tapping from track A and track B accents.

Anticipations occurred more frequently on track A respect than on track B ($F(1, 132)=41,300, p<0,01$).

Tapping performances on the shortest level (“events”) occurred more frequently on track B than on track A ($F(1, 132)=4,8065, p<0,05$). Further the standard deviation of time differences between tapping and events onsets was lower on track A than on track B ($F(1, 132)=352,99, p<0,01$). This means that synchronization was better (preciser) on track A, with higher rhythmical control than on track B (as claimed by Ashley, 2002).

4.2.3 Interaction between variables

The experimental results show a significant difference between expertise and track respect to anticipations ($F(1, 172)=11,784, p<0,01$). Indeed, experts performed on track A a constantly anticipated tapping respect to naïves on each experimental track, experts performed on track A a constantly anticipated tapping respect to experts on track B, but there were not significant

Figure 23. Interaction between expertise and track related to anticipations in tapping performance.

differences between groups on track B as figure 23 and table 2 show. In other words, this is an evidence that foreign meter affects more experts than naïves.

Table 2: Post Hoc (Newman-Keuls test):

	exp	brano	{1} ,56924	{2} ,49955	{3} ,80500	{4} ,56273
1	0	a		0,122105	0,000009	0,854596
2	0	b	0,122105		0,000008	0,075514
3	1	a	0,000009	0,000008		0,000022
4	1	b	0,854596	0,075514	0,000022	

It was also significantly different the interaction between expertise and track, related to the standard deviation of tapping times respect the music events ($F(1, 172)=4,0293, p<0,05$).

On track A, experts had a tapping performance with less standard deviations respect to naïve's tapping.

On track B, there were not observed differences related to tapping standard deviation. The results show that experts have a better timing on a familiar meter but there are not differences between groups on a foreign meter. (Figure 24, table 3).

Figure 24. Tapping standard deviation on track A and B performed by experts and naïves.

Table 3: Post hoc (Newman-Keuls test):

	exp	brano	{1} 60,845	{2} 121,60	{3} 44,358	{4} 120,40
1	0	a		0,000022	0,002203	0,000009
2	0	b	0,000022		0,000008	0,823368
3	1	a	0,002203	0,000008		0,000022
4	1	b	0,000009	0,823368	0,000022	

Another significant result was the interaction between track (A/B) and version⁷ on the tapping anticipations/delays ($F(10, 132)=2,5874, p<0,01$). The tapping times on track A - version “NTD” were less constantly anticipated than tapping times on track A - version “NE” ($p<0,05$) and on track A - version “NT” ($p<0,05$).

Finally I found a significant difference respect the tapping standard deviations between track and version ($F(10, 132)=2,6456, p<0,01$). In particular, the tapping times on track B - version “NTM” had more standard deviations than those on track B - version “OR” ($p<0,05$) and track B - version “NT” ($p<0,05$).

4.2.4 Comments from participants

Participants judged the tapping task from funny to annoying, in any case they easily performed the required task. The 40% of subjects said that it is quite constrictive a tapping performance with only one finger, but I found this method simple, effective and causing less biases than more free performances (as it would had been with two finger or two hands).

Usually experts evaluated their own tapping as well done, on the contrary naïves gave me various comments. Almost any subject said that tapping on track A (familiar meter) was easier.

Many subjects judged the trial task as difficult. I consider this comment as an index of good choice; in facts my intent was to provide a practice excerpt with a different meter respect to the experimental tracks.

Subjects reported several judgements about their own esthetics and emotions during the experimental tasks. Naïves commonly described the tracks as electronic or ethnic music.

Both the groups judged the music excerpts as repetitive. Track A was judged more familiar but not always it was preferred to the track B (asymmetric meter).

⁷ I created eleven versions of each track as described at §3.3.

4.3 Discussion

The present work has demonstrated the existence of significant differences between experts and naïve listeners in their synchronization behavior to a music piece with a naturalistic timing, but a modified accent structure and a meter which could be either familiar or unfamiliar. In fact, experts performed a better and faster entrainment to a familiar meter as compared to naïve listeners.

However, it is worth noting that (as compared to naïve listeners), experts began the task later, probably because they listened to the rhythm before starting to tap. Conversely, naïve listeners performed a gradual synchronization to the track. This outcome reveals a different cognitive attitude towards rhythm: experts have stronger (motor and perceptual) cognitive schemes, and begin the task once their schemes have matched the stimulus, whereas naïve listeners tend to rearrange their schemes according to the music.

These considerations agree with the results of pattern variability as a function of musical expertise. In fact, naïve listeners frequently change their patterns because they are in search of a more stable arrangement with music structure. On the other hand, experts show steadier behaviors.

This evidence leads us to another consideration. Naïve listeners are seeking for something, they try solutions, change their routes; their schemes are less structured, and therefore more flexible and fragile. An expert's performance might seem flatter and monotonous; yet it implies a deeper knowledge. As compared to naïve listeners, experts have a better knowledge of the structure, and are more sensitive to expressive timing variations. In fact, their tapping times are closer to music accents, constantly anticipated, and the differences between tapping times and music accents are less fluctuating⁸. Moreover, experts' tapping times are wider, hence, their attention considers more distant events.

⁸ Temporal differences between tapping times and corresponding events times constitute a sample. The experts' sample differs significantly from the naïve listeners' sample in its variance, as we can see in figure 24, respect to the track A. The experts' sample has a lower variance as compared to the naïve listeners' sample. This has important implications for how the two groups represent time. Any variability in keeping a precise tapping might be related to accuracy, i.e. the

The present work has also demonstrated that schemes are culturally based and cannot be merely exported to another context. This means that being an expert in presence of familiar structures does not guarantee to perform differently from a naïve subject when one is faced with a new, unknown context. Indeed, the results show that both anticipations and standard deviations made by experts are significantly different from those of naïve listeners only when they tap on track A (but not B). In other words, experts show a more precise tapping (as compared to naïve listeners) on a familiar meter, but not on unknown meters.

The results allow me to say that musicians are “expert” only within their own reference system, while when they operate in other reference systems, they have to use different schemes. In those situations, a strategy based on both assimilation and accommodation processes should be considered as more effective than one based on the sole accommodation of unknown accent structures to one’s own available schemes. Naïve listeners showed such an “assimilation-accommodation” strategy, whereas experts did not modify their behavior when faced with track B. Indeed, I observed the same speed of synchronization and the same number of patterns produced during the performance on track B.

The tapping patterns on track B have often more than one mode, and this can be related to a non-isochronous meter that causes fragmented patterns, made up of long and short lengths. Hence, I support the thesis of London (2004), who claims that human natural time can be made up of long and short durations and is not always isochronous. This statement is in agreement with the dynamic attending theory described in the first chapter, which predicts that the event temporal structure shapes a listener’s time, so that it is possible that a structure made up of different lengths will create a tactus made up of different lengths.

The present study demonstrated the preeminence of meter among melodic, dynamic and timbre structures in biasing a tapping performance, a result in line with previous works. Furthermore, this

magnitude of dispersions around the mean. I consider this as “temporal variability”. As compared to naïve listeners, experts keep more constant distances from the mean (i.e., lower temporal variability).

study showed no significant differences among melodic, dynamic and timbre structures in determining rhythmic cognition and time expression.

Indeed, I did find some differences among structures. Seemingly, the absence of more accented structures interferes with time cognition, but the results are still inconsistent, and I advocate further studies to address the issue appropriately. At the moment, I can suggest that the cognitive system might rely on a single accent structure among pitch, duration and timbre.

Our cognitive system might use one out of three sources of information independently to come to a representation of timing, both when these structures are consistent and in conflict. The experimental result support an independent perception of accent structure as proposed by Monahan & Carterette (1985), and Palmer & Krumhansl (1987), at least as long as melodic, dynamic and timbral information is concerned. Metric structure would instead be different from the others, being a hierarchical structure generated by higher-order cognitive processes (Penel & Drake, 1998), so that its change would at the same time affect the others.

On the basis of these considerations, it might be presumed that a mere modification of metrical, dynamic or timbral structure that violates cultural expectancies should not affect a tapping task, as it does not break any gestalt principle. Presumably, I should have obtained different results if manipulations had to break any of the gestalt principles mentioned in the first chapter.

I have reported an evidence in conflict with Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000). In fact, differently from their study, I did not observe differences in synchronization to expressive variations as compared to versions without any temporal variability.

Such evidence might however been justified if one considers the different musical pieces used in the above-mentioned and in this study. In fact, Drake, Penel & Bigand (2000) used pieces played according to a nineteenth-century style, which emphasize fluctuation in the metronomic pace. Conversely, in this experiment I used pieces with a strong rhythmic nature, hence with a lower temporal variability.

4.4 Conclusion

This investigation was aimed at improving our knowledge on the comprehension of asymmetrical rhythms from an intercultural point of view. Specifically, this study is one of the few to date focussing on cognition of asymmetrical meters and, as far as I know, the only study considering free tapping⁹ in relation to such meters.

In this study, I used real musical pieces. By using a digital editing procedure of sound signal, I manipulated various accent structures independently, and investigated their role in decoding rhythmic expression. This allowed us to investigate behavioural synchronization on the basis of a natural expressive variability, without the need for artificial stimuli. A software capable of precisely recording the tapping sessions was created, and a sound analytic methodology was proposed, supporting and extending our knowledge of the topic.

The main outcome of the present work has been the demonstration that the presumptive advantage of musicians (as compared to non-musicians) in synchronization behaviour fails in an intercultural context. Mental schemes built up during an educational training are specific to one's own cultural reference system, while they might not be beneficial in understanding unfamiliar structures.

A further element still unclear in cognitive research was the role melodic, timbral and dynamic structures play in rhythm detection and temporal variability. The present study demonstrated that our cognitive system is capable of using such structural information in a flexible way, for instance by discarding an incoherent structure in presence of conflicting conditions and reorienting towards other structures. Our cognitive system is also capable of extracting rhythm and timing by using one single accent structure (either melodic, timbral or dynamic structure), when it is consistent with one's own cultural schemes.

Finally, our results show that a musical piece whose temporal variability is consistent with its metrical structure allows a synchronization comparable to versions of the same piece without temporal variability. Such evidence, although inconsistent with a previous study (Drake, Penel &

⁹ A tapping not necessarily isochronous.

Bigand, 2000), supports the idea that behavioural synchronization occurs in human communication, which is made up of variable rhythms, rather than of metronomic durations.

Further studies using the same methodological procedure might shed new light onto the interactions between durational structure and other structures in determining rhythm and timing. Furthermore, they might focus on the role accent structures play, not only when expectancy schemes are violated, but also when metrical recurrences of other cultures are reconstructed.

Small changes inside the experimental software would allow the measurement of both tapping pressure and button press duration. Moreover, this investigation might be extended to investigate the role of emotions in rhythmic entrainment.

Appendix A: SPECTRAL ANALYSIS AND SIGNAL PROCESSING

The following table shows the series of the first 32 harmonics related to Track A and B (both in original version):

Brano A		Brano B	
Harmonics	Hertz	Harmonics	Hertz
1	123	1	150
2	242	2	298
3	366	3	447
4	487	4	597
5	608	5	748
6	732	6	893
7	851	7	1044
8	974	8	1190
9	1093	9	1341
10	1217	10	1491
11	1335	11	1642
12	1459	12	1787
13	1578	13	1938
14	1701	14	2089
15	1820	15	2239
16	1954	16	2390
17	2067	17	2536
18	2191	18	2686
19	2309	19	2837
20	2433	20	2988
21	2552	21	3136
22	2675	22	3284
23	2795	23	3434
24	2918	24	3585
25	3041	25	3732
26	3161	26	3882
27	3284	27	4032
28	3407	28	4178
29	3526	29	4328
30	3650	30	4479
31	3773	31	4630
32	3892	32	4780

Here the signal processing passages are explained in detail:

ORIGINAL VERSIONS

- Izotope (O2) Ozone 2 – *multiband stereo imaging*
 - Track A: *Band 1* freq 20-230 Hz, *widening* -0.36
 - Band 2* freq 230-1500 Hz, *widening* -0.73
 - Band 3* freq 1500-5500 Hz, *widening* -0,50
 - Band 4* freq 5500-20000 Hz, *widening* -0.32
 - Track B: *Band 1* freq 20-230 Hz, *widening* -0.34
 - Band 2* freq 230-1500 Hz, *widening* 0.48
 - Band 3* freq 1500-5500 Hz, *widening* 0.44
 - Band 4* freq 5500-20000 Hz, *widening* 0.01
- GRM Equalize Stereo (*Link channel L-R*)
 - Sliders 1-6*, -96 dB
- Normalize 0 dB

VERSIONS WITHOUT PITCH ACCENT STRUCTURE

- Tranceformer (*ring modulation*)
 - Track A: *Tone* 242 Hz
 - track B: *Tone* 298 Hz
- GRM Equalize Stereo (*Link channel L-R*)
 - Track A: *Sliders 1-8*, -96 dB
 - Sliders 9-14*, 0 dB
 - Slider 15*, -10 dB
 - Slider 16*, -37 dB
 - Sliders 17-21*, -75 dB
 - Slider 22*, -23 dB
 - Slider 23*, -8 dB
 - Sliders 24-31*, 0 dB
 - Track B: *Sliders 1-9*, -96 dB
 - Sliders 9-15*, 0 dB
 - Slider 16*, -23 dB
 - Slider 17*, -42 dB
 - Sliders 18-21*, -73 dB
 - Slider 22*, -35 dB
 - Slider 23-31*, 0 dB

VERSIONS WITHOUT DINAMIC ACCENT STRUCTURE

- VST Dynamics
 - Auto level* -25 db (*fast*)
 - Compressor: threshold* -15,5 db; *ratio* 8:1; *attack* 22,6 ms; *release* 50 ms
 - Limiters: threshold* -6 db; *release* 90 ms
- Wave X-noise
 - Threshold* 5,1; *Reduction* 77; *Attack* 35; *Release* 0
- *Fader out*: +5,8 db
- Izotope O2 (*postfader*)
 - Multiband dynamics: Compressor th* -7,5 db; *ra* 30:1; *att* 0 ms; *re* 73,4 ms

VERSIONS WHIT NOT COHERENT TIMBRE STRUCTURE

Next figure shows a fragment of signal processing where blue line describes the equalizer

frequency changes ($gain = +15\text{ db}$, $Q = 7.2$):

Before this passage, the signal was processed using the modules:

- North Pole: *cut off* 74; *Resonance* 59 (LP); *Env Follow* 99; *Attack* 34; *Release* 43
- Mysterizer as a *band pass filter*
- GRM Equalize Stereo (*Link channel* L-R)
 - Sliders* 1-11: -96 db
 - Sliders* 12-31: 0 db

The following image shows the sampling process to extract and split the events from each other.

The first pattern of a different waveform (according to the resulting sound) was sampled and it was considered the onset point.

(zoom):

Appendix B: SEXPERIMENTAL SOFTWARE

By the use of Max/MSP 4.5 programming environment, I developed a software to record the tapping times and write a list of cumulative and relative times in a text file.

Once I had the times of a performance I could match the corresponding experimental tracks times.

This software is “stand alone” and it can run on Windows operating system.

Here I show a functional flow chart of the software:

The following figure shows the software's user interface and it explains its usage:

At the end of an experimental session, the software delivered a text file containing a list of cumulative times and a list of Inter Onset Intervals.

REFERENCES

- Agamennone, M., Facci, S., Giannattasio, F., Giurati, G. (1991). *Grammatica della musica etnica*. Roma, Bulzoni editore.
- Andolfi, M. (2000). *Il colloquio relazionale*. Roma, RISA.
- Aschersleben, G., & Prinz, W. (1995). Synchronizing actions with events: The role of sensory information. *Perception and Psychophysics*, 57, 305-317.
- Ashley, R. (2002). Do[n't] change a hair for me: the art of jazz rubato. *Music Perception*, 19(3), 311-332.
- Brailoiu, C. (1973). Le rythme Aksak (ed. or. 1951), in *Problèmes d'Ethnomusicologie*, Minkoff Reprint, Genève., pp. 303-340.
- Bregman, A. S. (1990). *Auditory scene analysis: the perceptual organization of sound*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Bregman, A. S. (1993). Auditory scene analysis: Hearing in complex environments. In McAdams S. & Bigand E. (ed.). *Thinking in sound – The cognitive psychology of human audition*. Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Clarke, E. F. (1985). Structure and expression in rhythmic performance. In P. Howell, I. Cross & R. West (ed.), *Musical structure and cognition*. London, Academic Press, 1985, pp. 209-236.
- Clarke, E. F. (1989). The perception of expressive timing in music. *Psychological Research*, 51(1), 2-9.

- Clarke, E. F. (1999). Rhythm and timing in music. In D. Deutsch (ed.) *The psychology of music* 2nd edition (pp. 473-499). London, Academic Press.
- Collier, G. L., & Collier J. L. (2002). A study of timing in two Louis Armstrong solos. *Music Perception, 19*(3), 463-483.
- Cooper, G., & Meyer, L.B. (1960). *The rhythmic structure of music*. Chicago, University of Chicago Press.
- Cross, I. (2003). Music, cognition, culture, and evolution. In *The cognitive neuroscience of music*. Oxford, University Press.
- Dixon, S. & Goebel, W. (2002). Pinpointing the beat: tapping to expressive performances. 7th *International Conference on Music Perception and Cognition (ICMPC7)*, Sydney, July.
- Dowling, W. J., & Harwood, D. L. (1986). *Music cognition*. Orlando, FL: Academic Press.
- Drake, C. (1993). Reproduction of musical rhythms by children, adult musicians and nonmusicians. *Perception and Psychophysics, 53*, 25-33.
- Drake, C., & Bertrand, D. (2003). The quest for universals in temporal processing in music. In I. Peretz, R. Zatorre (ed.) *The cognitive neuroscience of music*. Oxford, University Press.
- Drake, C., Jones, M. R., & Baruch, C., (2000). The development of rhythmic attending in auditory sequences: attunement, referent period, focal attending. *Cognition 77*, 251-288
- Drake, C., & Palmer, C. (1993). Accent structures in music performance. *Music Perception, 10*(3), 343-378.
- Drake, C., Penel, A., & Bigand, E. (2000). Tapping in time with mechanically and expressively performed music. *Music Perception, 18*, 1-23.

- Giannattasio, F. (1998). *Il concetto di musica*. Roma, Bulzoni editore.
- Huber, D. M., & Runstein, R. E. (1999). *Manuale della registrazione sonora*. Milano, Hoepli editore.
- Ivry, B., & Hazeltine, R. E. (1995). Perception and production of temporal intervals across a range of durations: evidence for a common timing mechanism. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, *21*, 3-18.
- Iyer, V. (2002). Embodied mind, situated cognition, and expressive microtiming in African-American music. *Music Perception*, *19*(3), 387-414.
- Jones, M. R. (1990a). Learning and the development of expectancies: an interactionist approach. *Psychomusicology*, *9*(2), 193-228.
- Jones, M. R. (1990b). Musical events and models of musical time. In R. A. Block, *Cognitive models of musical time*. pp207-240. Erlbaum, Hillsdale, NJ.
- Jones, M. R., & Boltz, M. (1989). Dynamic attending and responses to time. *Psychological Review*, *96*(3), 459-491.
- Jones, M. R., Boltz, M., & Kidd, G. (1982). Controlled attending as a function of melodic and temporal context. *Perception & Psychophysics*, *32*(3), 211-218.
- Jones, M. R., Moynihan, H., Mac Kensie, N. & Puente, J. (2002). Temporal aspect of stimulus-driven attending in dynamic arrays. *Psychological Science*, *13*(4), 313-319.
- Jones, M. R., & Yee, W. (1993). Attending to auditory events: the role of temporal organization. In S. McAdams & E. Bigand (ed.). *Thinking in sound – The cognitive psychology of human audition*. Oxford, Clarendon Press.
- Karolyi O. (2000) *La grammatica della musica. La teoria, le forme e gli strumenti musicali*. Torino. Piccola biblioteca Einaudi.

- Kendall, R. A. & Carterette, E. C. (1990). The communication of musical expression. *Music Perception*, 8(2), 129-164.
- Large, E. W., & Jones, M. R. (1999). The dynamics of attending: how we track time varying events. *Psychological Review*, 106(1), 119–159.
- Large, E., & Pamer, C. (2002). Perceiving temporal regularity in music. *Cognitive Science* 26, 1–37
- Larson, S. (2002). Musical forces, melodic expectation, and jazz melody. *Music Perception*, 19(3), 351-386.
- Lichtenberg, J. D. (1995). *Psicoanalisi e sistemi motivazionali*. Milano, Raffaello Cortina Editore.
- London, J. (2004). *Hearing in time. Psychological aspect of musical meter*. Oxford, University Press.
- Meyer, R. K., & Palmer, C., (2003). Temporal and motor transfer in music performance. *Music Perception*, 21(1), 81-104.
- Moelants, D. (2003). Tempo, meter and perception of Aksak meters. Meeting of the Society for music perception & cognition, June 16-19. Las Vegas, UNLV.
- Monahan, C. B., & Carterette, E. C. (1985). Pitch and duration as determinants of musical space. *Music Perception*, 3(1), 1-32.
- Narmour, E. (1999). Hierarchical expectation and musical style. In D. Deutsch (ed.) *The psychology of music* 2nd edition (pp. 441-472). London, Academic Press.
- Neri, C. (1998). *Gruppo*. Roma, edizioni Borla.
- Palmer, C. (1989). Mapping musical thought to musical performance. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception & Performance*, 15, 331–346.

- Palmer, C. (1996). Anatomy of a performance: sources of musical expression. *Music Perception*, 13(3), 433-453.
- Palmer, C., & Krumhansl, C. L. (1987). Independent temporal and pitch structures in the determination of musical phrases. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 13, 116-126.
- Palmer, C., & Meyer, R. K. (2000). Conceptual and motor learning in music performance. *Psychological Science*, 11, 63-68.
- Parncutt, R. (1994). A perceptual model of pulse salience and metrical accent in musical rhythms. *Music Perception*, 11(4), 409-464.
- Penel, A., Drake, C. (1998). Sources of timing variation in music performance: A psychological segmentation model. *Psychological Research*, 61(1), 12-32.
- Pfordresher, P. Q. (2003). The role of melodic and rhythmic accents in musical structure. *Music Perception*, 20(4), 431-464.
- Povel, D. & Essens, P. (1985). Perception of temporal patterns. *Music Perception*, 2, 411-441.
- Purwins, H., Blankertz, B., & Obermayer, K. (2000). Computing auditory perception. *Organised Sound* 5 (3): 159–171. Cambridge, University Press.
- Rasch, R., & Plomp, R. (1999). The perception of musical tones. In D. Deutsch (ed.) *The psychology of music* 2nd edition (pp. 441-472). London, Academic Press.
- Repp, B. H. (1997). Expressive timing in a Debussy Prelude: a comparison of student and expert pianists. *Musicae Scientiae* 1(2), 257-268.
- Repp, B. H. (1998). Obligatory “expectations” of expressive timing induced by perception of musical structure. *Psychological Research*, 61(1), 33-43.

- Repp, B. H. (1999). Detecting deviations from metronomic timing in music: effect of perceptual structure on the mental timekeeper. *Perception & Psychophysics*, *61*(3), 529-548.
- Repp, B. H. (2000). Pattern typicality and dimensional interaction in pianists' imitation of expressive timing and dynamics. *Music Perception*, *18*(2), 173-211.
- Risset, J. C., & Wessel, D. L. (1999). Exploration of timbre By Analysis and synthesis. In D. Deutsch (ed.) *The psychology of music* 2nd edition (pp. 113-169). London, Academic Press.
- Rizzolatti, G., Fadiga, L., Fogassi, L., & Gallese, V. (1999). Resonance behaviours and mirror neurons. *Archives Italiennes de Biologie*, *137*(2-3), 85-100.
- Rosenthal, D. (1992). Emulation of human rhythm perception. *Computer Music Journal*, *16*(1): 64-76.
- Sachs, C. (1979). *Le sorgenti della musica*. Torino, Boringhieri editore.
- Schogler, B. W. (1999). Studying temporal co-ordination in jazz duets. *Musicae Scientiae*, special issue, 1999-2000, 75-92.
- Snyder, J., & Krumhansl, C. L. (2001). Tapping to ragtime: cues to pulse finding. *Music Perception*, *18*(4), 455-489.
- Todd, N. P. M. (1992). The dynamics of dynamics: a model of musical expression. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, *91*, 3540-3550.
- Toiviainen, P., & Snyder, J. S. (2003). Tapping to Bach : resonance-based modeling of pulse. *Music Perception*, *21*(1), 43-80.
- Trehub, S. E. (2003). Musical predispositions in infancy: an update. In *The cognitive neuroscience of music*. Oxford, University Press.

van Noorden, L. P. A. S. (1975). Temporal coherence in the perception of tone sequences. Ph. D. Thesis, Eindhoven University of Technology, The Netherlands.

Vastfjall, D., Larsson, P., & Kleiner, M. (2002). Emotion and auditory virtual environments: affect-based judgments of music reproduced with virtual reverberation times. *Behaviour*, 5(1), 19-32.

Warren, R. M. (1993). Perception of acoustic sequences: global integration versus temporal resolution. In S. McAdams & E. Bigand (ed). *Thinking in sound – The cognitive psychology of human audition*. Oxford, Clarendon Press.

Warren, R. M. & Ackroff, J. M. (1976). Two types of auditory sequence perception. *Perception and Psychophysics*, 20, 387-394.

Windsor, W. L., & Clarke, E. F. (1997). Expressive timing and dynamics in real and artificial musical performances: using an algorithm as an analytical tool. *Music Perception*, 15(2), 127-152.

REFERENCES ON THE WEB ABOUT JEWS HARP

<http://www.bandatolfa.it/pagine%20strumenti/scacciapensieri.htm>.

<http://www.jewsharpguild.org>

<http://www.jewsharpguild.org/play.html>

<http://www.pertout.com/Jew'sHarp.htm>